

Yttrium and lanthanide nitrate complexes of 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl-[2'-(aminomethyl)pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazoline-5-one

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Abstract : A series of complexes of the Schiff base 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl-[2'-(aminomethyl)pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazoline-5-one (L) with the general composition $[Ln(L)_2(NO_3)_2](NO_3)$ (where Ln = Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho or Er) has been synthesized and characterized. L is a neutral ligand donating through the carbonyl oxygen and the azomethine nitrogen in these complexes. Two nitrate ions are bidentately coordinate in these complexes. The covalency parameters evaluated from solid and solution state electronic spectra suggest the weak covalent character of the metal-ligand bond. A coordination number of eight is assigned to the metal ion in these complexes.

Keywords : Lanthanide, complexes, yttrium, ligand, synthesis.

Introduction

By the last three decades, a great deal of attention has been devoted to the study of Schiff base complexes owing to their pharmacological applications¹ and antibacterial^{2,3} as well as anti-inflammatory properties⁴. Rare earth metal complexes of pyrazolone derived Schiff bases are relatively less investigated although a quantitative information about these would be of high interest. In view of this, here, as an extension of our studies on rare earth nitrate complexes with antipyrene derivatives⁵⁻¹⁰, we report the synthesis and characterization of a new pyrazolone derived Schiff base and its complexes with some rare earth nitrates. The ligand L (Fig. 1) and its complexes with yttrium and lanthanide nitrates would be expected to be of physiological importance.

Experimental

Antipyrene-4-carboxaldehyde and 2-(aminomethyl)pyridine were purchased from M/s. Aldrich Chem. Co., USA. Yttrium and lanthanide nitrates were prepared by dissolving the respective oxides (99.9%) (M/s. Rare Earths Ltd., Kerala or M/s. Aldrich Chem. Co., USA) in 60% AR nitric acid (Merck) and then by crystallizing out the salt by evaporating the solution on a steam bath. Solvents used were either GPR or AR grade (Merck, India; BDH, India or SRL, India). The Schiff base and complexes were

Fig. 1. 2,3-Dimethyl-4-formyl-[2'-(aminomethyl)pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazoline-5-one (L).

analyzed for the elements carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen on a Heraeus CHNO rapid analyzer and the metal gravimetrically as oxides¹¹. Molar conductance in dimethylformamide, methanol and nitrobenzene (10^{-3} M solutions) were measured at room temperature using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge with a dip-type cell of platinum electrodes (cell constant 1.1008). The IR spectra of Schiff base and complexes were recorded in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} on a Shimadzu IR 470 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra in solid state (paste with Nujol) and solution in dimethylformamide and methanol (10^{-3} M) were recorded in the range 200–1100 nm on a Shimadzu UV 160A spectrophotometer. The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR

spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-500 spectrometer using DMSO- d_6 as solvent.

Preparation of 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl-[2'-(aminomethyl)-pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazoline-5-one (L) :

To a boiling solution of 10 mmol of 2-(aminomethyl)-pyridine (1.0815 g) in ethanol (20 mL), 10 mmol of anti-pyridine-4-carboxaldehyde (2.1624 g) in ethanol (30 mL) was added and refluxed on a steam bath for about 6 h. The precipitated light brown crystals were filtered and washed with cold ethanol to remove the unreacted reactants, if any. It was then recrystallized from ethyl acetate and dried over phosphorus(V)oxide under vacuum. The purity was checked by TLC, infrared spectrum and elemental analyses.

Preparation of the complexes :

One mmol of the rare earth nitrate in methanol (10 mL) was added to a boiling solution of 2.1 mmol of the Schiff base (0.7022 g) in ethanol (20 mL) and kept under reflux for about 4 h. The crystalline solid complexes formed on cooling were filtered and washed with water and hot benzene subsequently to remove any excess of reactants. It was then recrystallized from methanol and dried over phosphorus(V)oxide under vacuum.

Results and discussion

From the elemental analyses results, the complexes may be formulated as $\text{LnL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_3$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho}$ or Er). They are non-hygroscopic solids soluble in acetone, DMF, DMSO, ethanol, methanol and nitrobenzene but insoluble in acetonitrile, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ethyl acetate, toluene and water.

The observed values of the electrical conductance of the complexes in three non aqueous solvents, viz. DMF ($\sim 82 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), methanol ($\sim 109 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and nitrobenzene ($\sim 28 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) are in good agreement with the results of Geary¹² and suggest 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviors for all the complexes. Thus the complexes may be formulated as $[\text{LnL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho}$ or Er).

IR spectra :

The IR spectrum of L exhibits a strong absorption at 1660 cm^{-1} corresponding to the stretching vibration of the pyrazolone carbonyl group^{6,13}. The band observed at

1562 cm^{-1} is attributed to the azomethine ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) stretching vibrations¹³. The shift of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ frequencies to around 1618 cm^{-1} and 1585 cm^{-1} respectively in the complexes indicates the chelation of the ligand through the carbonyl oxygen and the azomethine nitrogen⁵. The bands at 1430 cm^{-1} and 720 cm^{-1} for the ligand are ascribed to the ring stretching and out-of-plane deformation modes of the pyridine part of the ligand¹³. Both the bands remain unaltered in complexes indicating the non-coordinating nature of pyridine ring nitrogen atom in complexes. Furthermore, the complexes show bands corresponding to both coordinated and ionic nitrates. The strong band at 1385 cm^{-1} is assigned to the ν_3 (D_{3h}) vibration^{5,9} of the ionic nitrate. The bands at about 1488 cm^{-1} and 1285 cm^{-1} are attributed to suggest the presence of coordinated nitrate group of C_{2v} symmetry^{9,14}. The medium band about 1068 cm^{-1} due to ν_2 vibrations of the nitrate group (C_{2v}) stands as an additional evidence for the presence of coordinated nitrate⁸. The difference in wave number between the two highest frequency bands ($\nu_4-\nu_1$) of the nitrate group having C_{2v} symmetry is about 203 cm^{-1} which indicates that, the coordinated nitrate ions are bidentate^{15,16}. The $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ stretching vibrations are observed around 465 and 450 cm^{-1} respectively⁷.

Electronic spectra :

The absorption spectrum of the ligand L shows two maxima at 40387 and 29832 cm^{-1} which corresponds to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions respectively¹⁸. In complexes, these bands shift to the regions $39766-40009$ and $25906-27322 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $f-f$ bands are observed only in the case of Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} , Dy^{III} , Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes and for other lanthanide complexes, the bands could not be identified as they are presumably masked by the ligand charge transfer transitions¹⁸⁻²⁰. The band shift compared to those of aqua ions [$\Delta\nu = \nu(\text{com}) - \nu(\text{aquo})$] may be used as a measure of the metal-ligand covalent bonding²¹. The $f-f$ transition frequencies along with tentative assignments^{22,23} are given in Table 1. Calculations using $\Delta\nu$ suggest weak covalent character to the metal-ligand bond. The spectral profile of hypersensitive bands of Nd^{III} , Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes closely resembles that of eight coordinated complexes reported by Karrakar^{24,25} and is in good agreement with the other physico-chemical investigations. The spectral features of complexes are similar

Table 1. *f-f* Transitions of the nitrate complexes of Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy, Ho and Er with L

Complex	Abs. max (cm ⁻¹)	Molar extinction coefficients ^e (ε)		Tentative assignments	Bonding parameters
		DMF	MeOH		
[Pr(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	22471	16.45	18.35	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂	β = 0.9983
	21276	18.22	19.02	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₁	b ^{1/2} = 0.0206
	20703	9.35	10.11	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₀	δ = 0.1703
	16835	8.78	9.96	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	η = 0.0008
[Nd(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	19379	14.55	17.16	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ G _{9/2}	β = 0.9975
	13437	17.81	21.08	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{7/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0328
	12492	6.36	9.77	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2}	δ = 0.4319
	11527	7.48	9.08	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{3/2}	η = 0.0022
[Sm(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	24026	21.36	23.47	⁶ H _{5/2} → (⁶ P, ⁴ P) _{5/2}	β = 0.9975
	20986	3.56	5.56	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{11/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0250
	20618	14.09	16.20	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ M _{15/2}	δ = 0.2506
	10504	12.40	15.13	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{11/2}	η = 0.0013
[Dy(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	25839	8.96	10.41	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{13/2}	β = 0.9957
	22123	11.12	13.32	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{15/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0328
	13212	3.54	5.08	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{3/2}	δ = 0.1603
	12432	4.65	6.17	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{5/2}	η = 0.0022
[Ho(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	11025	14.05	15.19	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{7/2}	
	23866	20.21	22.08	⁵ I ₈ → (⁵ G ₃ , ³ G) ₅	β = 0.9985
	22075	6.32	8.45	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ G ₅	b ^{1/2} = 0.0194
	21119	10.75	11.97	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₂	δ = 0.1502
[Er(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	20576	4.86	6.16	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₃	η = 0.0008
	18587	9.88	11.24	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₄	
	15503	3.78	5.16	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₅	
	24479	19.85	21.10	⁴ I _{15/2} → (² G, ⁴ F) _{9/2}	β = 0.9989
[Er(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	22421	7.48	9.78	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.166
	20408	4.62	6.56	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{7/2}	δ = 0.1101
	19212	20.11	21.97	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ H _{11/2}	η = 0.0006
	18450	16.13	17.98	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ S _{3/2}	
	15220	5.76	7.13	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{9/2}	
	10209	11.83	14.23	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ I _{11/2}	

both in the solid state and in solution (DMF and methanol), indicating the identical stoichiometry and coordination number in solid as well as in solution phase.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectrum of L and its yttrium as well as lanthanum nitrate complexes at room temperature are presented in Table 2 along with their assignments. The coordination through azomethine nitrogen²⁶ is confirmed since the (-N=C-H) singlet at 8.42 ppm is shifted to a down field, i.e. to 8.10–8.12 ppm in yttrium and lanthanum complexes. The broad multiplet in the region 7.23–7.67 ppm is attributable to the phenyl protons of pyrazolone.

It is shifted to the regions 7.20–7.62 ppm which may be due to the coordination¹⁹ of the carbonyl oxygen. The multiplet in the region 7.14–8.67 ppm due to pyridyl ring remain practically unaltered which rules out the coordination²⁷ of pyridyl nitrogen.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR of L as well as its yttrium and lanthanide complexes are presented in Table 3. The resonance signal at 166.73 ppm in L due to C₍₁₄₎ is shifted to 147.42 ppm in complexes showing the coordination of azomethine nitrogen²⁸ and the shifts of C₍₄₎ and C₍₅₎ to 100.44 and 169.30 ppm respectively indicate the coordination²⁸ of ring carbonyl oxygen.

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data (ppm) of L and its yttrium and lanthanum nitrate complexes

L		[Y(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)		[La(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)		Assignment
B	I	B	I	B	I	
2.55	19.10	2.55	38.20	2.55	38.20	C—CH ₃ 13
3.34	19.10	3.34	38.20	3.34	38.20	N—CH ₃ 12
3.71	1.42	3.85	3.69	3.85	3.69	N—CH ₂ —C 16
8.42	3.19	8.10	12.73	8.12	12.73	H C=N 14 C
7.67	1.91	7.62	3.02	7.62	3.02	
7.46	1.37	7.20	2.42	7.20	2.42	
7.23	0.92	7.21	3.42	7.21	3.42	
7.46	0.32	7.22	3.09	7.22	3.12	
7.67	1.93	7.62	3.02	7.62	3.02	
8.67	0.40	8.69	0.80	8.69	0.80	
7.14	0.44	7.14	0.85	7.14	0.85	
7.74	0.43	7.74	0.85	7.74	0.85	
7.21	0.84	7.40	0.91	7.40	0.91	

B = Band position and I = Intensity.

Table 3. ¹³C NMR spectral data (ppm) of L and its yttrium and lanthanum nitrate complexes

L	[Y(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	[La(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂](NO ₃)	Assignment
8.13	8.13	8.13	C—CH ₃ 13
37.62	37.60	37.60	N—CH ₃ 12
144.35	124.81	124.84	N=C—H 14a
161.30	161.30	161.30	
109.20	100.01	100.02	
164.80	166.30	166.31	
147.26	147.26	147.26	
123.28	125.31	125.31	
130.69	127.62	127.62	
126.47	126.61	126.61	
130.69	127.62	127.62	
123.28	125.31	125.31	
168.47	164.43	164.45	
132.49	131.24	131.24	
127.67	138.32	138.32	
129.35	129.97	129.97	
134.47	133.04	133.04	
129.35	129.97	129.97	
127.67	138.32	138.32	

On the basis of analytical and spectral data the tentative structure of the complexes may be assigned as follows (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. [LnL₂(NO₃)₂](NO₃) (Ln = Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho or Er).

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